

COUPLED ELECTRICAL POTENTIAL AND IN-PLANE LOAD RESPONSE IN STRUCTURAL BATTERIES

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Working principle of a lithium ion battery

Carlstedt et al., *Electro-chemo-mechanically coupled computational modelling of structural batteries*, *Multifunct. Mater.* 3 (2020). doi:10.1088/2399-7532/abc60d.

Design, realisation and characterization of structural battery composites

Asp et al., A Structural Battery and its Multifunctional Performance, *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* 2000093 (2021) 2000093.
doi:10.1002/aesr.202000093.

Carbon fibres in a structural battery composite

- 2014, KTH

2016, Hagberg et al.

2018, Fredi et al.

2022, Duan et al.

2021, Johansen et al.

Piezo-electrochemical effect in lithium-intercalated carbon fibres

Jacques E. *Electrochem. Commun.* 35 (2013) 65–67

PECT-effect in structural battery composite negative electrode

How is the structural battery affected by mechanical loading?

Material and method

Gamry potentiostat

Deben 2kN micro tester

Alternating mechanical and electrochemical loads

What is the effect on potential from
simultaneous mechanical loading?

Strain sensitivity in structural batteries

k - coupling factor

$$k = \Delta E / \Delta \epsilon$$

Results

Cell A – discharged

Displacement rate 0.2 mm/min (Strain rate $95 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$)

Displacement rate 0.5 mm/min (Strain rate $24 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$)

Results

Cell B – fully charged

Displacement rate 0.2 mm/min (Strain rate $95 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$)

Displacement rate 0.5 mm/min (Strain rate $24 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$)

Results

Coupling factor $k = \Delta E / \Delta \varepsilon$

Cell	State of charge [%]	Displacement rate [mm/min]	Coupling factor [V / unit strain]
A	0	0.2	0.84
		0.5	0.82
B	100	0.2	0.64
		0.5	0.69

Conclusions

- Establishment of the test method.
- Increase in mechanical load → decrease in potential
- Linear elastic behavior of the coupling factor

Acknowledgements

- Swedish National Space Agency, project no. 2020-00256;
- USAF, EOARD Award No. FA8655-21-1-7038;
- ONR, USA, Award No. N62909-22-1-2037

The authors acknowledge the contribution by the MSc students Samia Tasneem; Elias Elmqvist; Zhaoyang Li via the Chalmers' TRACKS course TRA105 on Structural Battery Composites.

